

Comparative performance of cotton subjected to organic and synthetic fertilizer under protected and unprotected conditions of insects

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ABSTRACT

Results under unprotected conditions indicated that total yield was significantly higher in recommended fertilizer conditions (18.14 q/ha) when compared with FYM (16.51 q/ha) and Control (15.86 q/ha), whereas the yield attributing characters like plant height, number of monopods/ plant, number of sympods/ plant and number of bolls/plant were non-significant in all the treatment. In case of protected conditions the average total yield of all treatments (20.67 q/ ha) as well as the number of boll/ plant (43.0) was significantly higher as compared to the unprotected conditions. Simultaneously the average populations of jassid (1.63/ 3 leaves), whitefly (1.52/ 3 leaves) and thrips (1.38/ 3 leaves) were less under protected conditions as compared to the unprotected conditions where it was 2.01, 2.39 and 2.54 per 3 leaves, respectively. However, the population of natural enemies (spider, *Chrysoperla carnea* and *Coccinella septempunctata*) was high in unprotected conditions where fertilizers was applied.

Owing to favorable combination of several factors namely, better quality inputs improved production techniques like IPM, IRM etc. and to some extent large scale adoptions of Bt-cotton hybrids, the productivity of cotton has increased from 369 kg lint in 2001 to 599 kg lint in 2007-08. To undo the ill effects that have crept in current agricultural scenario (use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides) while attempting to increase cotton production in the prevalent cropping systems, the organic protocols of farming could accentuate and aid in imparting improved momentum to the bio dynamics of crop fields. Although cotton is a heavy feeder, when compared with other field crops yet the nutrient requirements are not as high as in most vegetables. Soil mineral levels are built up through application of animal manure, compost and soluble rock phosphate etc. Organic farming practices which require low cost and low external input production system with organic methods can impart stability in production eventually improving the sustainability. In the present study performance of cotton crop supplied with different type of nutrient under protected and unprotected conditions was assessed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at experimental area of Regional Station, PAU, Bathinda during 2005-06 and 2006-07. The cotton variety F-1861 with three treatments *ie.* T1- recommended fertilizer (150 kg urea+ 30 kg DAP); T2- FYM (@ 10 tones/ ha) and T3- no fertilizer condition was sown under two different situations of protected and unprotected conditions (Refer Table 1, 2, 3). In protected conditions applications of insecticides like imidacloprid, triazophos, acephate and chlorpyrifos were applied as and when the need arise. To minimize the risk of drifting of insecticides from protected to unprotected conditions a 10 meter wide strip of sorghum was sown in between two different sets which also helped in providing shelter to natural enemies.

The data for sucking pests like jassids, thrips and whitefly per three leaves was recorded both from protected and unprotected conditions simultaneously the data for natural enemies like spider, lace wing and lady bird beetle per plant was also recorded. The crop as well as plant parameters like plant height (cm.), monopods per plant, sympods per plant, no. of bolls per plant as well as the seed cotton yield was recorded both from protected and unprotected conditions. The data were analyzed statistically.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As per the data illustrated in Table and Fig. 1 regarding the characters of cotton, the height was more in T1 (recommended fertilizer) treatment in protected conditions but statistically it was at par with other treatments. Similarly there was no significant difference in monopods and sympods per plant which were similar in all the treatments both under protected and unprotected conditions. Though the number of bolls per plant was insignificant in all the treatments of manure and fertilizer but there was significant difference in protected and unprotected conditions and it was significantly higher in protected conditions (43 bolls/ plant in protected as compared to 32 bolls/ plant in unprotected conditions). The seed cotton yield obtained was significantly higher in recommended fertilizer conditions as compare to FYM(T2) and no fertilizer (T3) conditions but among protected and unprotected conditions the yield was significantly higher in sprayed conditions (20.67 q/ha).

Fig. 1. Yield and insect pests of cotton under protected and unprotected conditions

The data recorded for insect pests and natural enemies in all the treatments both under protected and unprotected conditions revealed comparatively more population of jassid, whitefly and thrip in unprotected conditions (2.01, 2.39, 2.54/3 leaves, respectively) as compared to protected conditions (1.63, 1.53, 1.38/ 3 leaves, respectively) but with in treatments the recommended fertilizer plots were having the highest population of jassids, whitefly and thrips as compare to FYM @ 10 tone/ ha and no fertilizer condition (Table 2 and Fig 1). The study lend credence from the finding of Kowalski and Visser (1979), Palti (1981), Campbell (1989), Hendrix *et al.* (1990), Magdoff (1992), Attieri (1994), Morales *et al.* (1997), Leal *et al.* (1997) and Myers and Stilton (1999) and Ahmed *et al.* (2002) where the population of sucking pests was reported significantly higher on crops grown with synthetic/ inorganic fertilizers.

The population of natural enemies like, lady bird beetle (*Coccinella* spp.), lacewing (*Chrysoperla carnea*) and spiders was high under unprotected condition and among the various treatments recommended FYM @ 10 q/ha was found to harbour the maximum population of lady bird beetle (0.46/ plant) where as the population of lacewing and spider was higher in recommended fertilizer situations (Table 3). The population of bollworm like, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Earias insulana*, *E. vittella* and *Pecinophora gossypiella* was not observed and the damage to the fruiting bodies was found negligible as in 2005-06 and 2006-07 the incidence of bollworm was less.

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Table 1. Effect of protected and unprotected treatment on different characters of cotton.

Treatments	Plant height (cm)	Monopods Per plant	Sympods Per plant	No. of bolls/plant	Seed cotton yield (q/ha)
Protected	155.6	2.18	27.97	43.00	20.67
Unprotected	151.4	2.42	28.95	32.80	13.01
CD at 5%	NS	NS	NS	4.20	1.21
No fertilizer	145.8	2.35	28.45	36.40	15.86
FYM @ 10 t/ha	153.2	2.25	20.03	37.30	16.51
Recommended fertilizer	161.6	2.30	28.90	40.00	18.14
CD at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.17

Table 2. Average population of sucking pests under protected and unprotected conditions in cotton.

Treatments	Jassid/ 3 leaves	Whitefly/ 3 leaves	Thrips/ 3 leaves
Protected	1.63	1.52	1.38
Unprotected	2.01	2.39	2.54
CD at 5%	0.32	0.40	0.58
No fertilizer	1.53	1.91	1.82
FYM @ 10 t/ha	1.73	1.35	1.22
Recommended fertilizer	2.24	2.64	2.85
CD at 5%	0.26	0.58	0.71

Table 3. Average population of natural enemies under protected and unprotected conditions in cotton.

Treatments	Spider/ plant	Chrysoperla/ plant	Coccinellid/ plant
Protected	0.38	0.36	0.31
Unprotected	0.59	0.54	0.47
CD at 5%	0.19	0.13	0.14
No fertilizer	0.37	0.35	0.30
FYM @ 10 t/ha	0.52	0.46	0.46
Recommended fertilizer	0.56	0.54	0.42
CD at 5%	0.08	0.013	0.097

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